

INTERFACIAL STRENGTH IN PEEK/CARBON COMPOSITE

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ABSTRACT

Although interfacial crystallinity is found to be essential to insure optimum interfacial strength in PEEK/carbon composites, it seems that it is not the primary parameter responsible for the fiber/matrix interaction. The present work shows that this is probably a result of several complex mechanisms such as matrix adsorption on the fiber surface, matrix reaction leading to chemical bonding, and interfacial crystallization. The concept of adsorption proposed by Brady and Porter for the polycarbonate/carbon fiber system seems to be valid to interpret the evolution with time under isothermal conditions of the short beam shear strength, as described by a Langmuir-type expression. The temperature dependence of the formation of the fiber/matrix interaction as measured by the short beam shear strength is also found to follow an Arrhenius equation, with an activation energy of 324 kJ mol⁻¹.

1. INTRODUCTION

It is well known that the structure and properties of the fiber/matrix interface play a major role in determining the mechanical and physical properties of composite materials. However, the nature of the fiber/matrix interaction, especially in the case of thermoplastic composites, is among the least understood aspects of composite materials. In the case of PEEK/carbon fiber composite, some authors have suggested that the outstanding fiber/matrix strength observed in the APC-2 (AS4/PEEK) composite is strongly related to the ability of the PEEK matrix to produce a transcrystalline layer around the carbon fibers [1, 2]. However, it has been shown by Hartness [3] and Lustiger [4] that the low modulus AS4 fiber has a significantly lower nucleation tendency than the high modulus HMS fiber, which easily generates transcrystallinity in PEEK but yet leads to very low transverse flexural strength in comparison with that of the AS4/PEEK composite. Moreover, from most of the morphological studies reported on molded APC-2 AS4/PEEK composite, it appears that transcrystalline structure is a negligible element of the global crystallinity of the PEEK matrix. Peacock *et al* [5-7] have reported that etched surfaces of molded APC-2 composite characterized by good fiber/matrix adhesion and well-developed spherulites do not show any transcrystallinity at the fiber/matrix interface. Also, Lustiger [4] has pointed out that columnar crystalline structure along the carbon fibers has been observed only in a specific region of a very slowly cooled specimen.

Recently, Brady and Porter [8] have shown that the concept of adsorption can be used to explain the interfacial improvement in the annealed polycarbonate/carbon fiber system and they have suggested that this concept would also explain the results of Lee and Porter [2]. In this work, the increase of the transverse tensile strength of PEEK/carbon fiber (PAN-based Thornel-300) composite observed with increasing time above the melting point, which was attributed to better transcrystallinity, seems to be more appropriately explained by better adsorption. Moreover, Schultz *et al* [9] have also shown a linear relationship between the work of adhesion (estimated from the dispersive component of the surface energy and the acid-base character of the carbon fiber and the PEEK matrix) and the

interfacial shear strength of the composite determined by means of a fragmentation test. They concluded that this result indicates that physicochemical interactions determine the mechanical behavior of the fiber/matrix interface. This conclusion supports the assumption of adsorption as a mechanism for increased adhesion in thermoplastic/carbon fiber composite.

In previous work on optimization of the processing of PEEK/carbon composite made from both APC-2 prepreg and NCS-1025 commingled fabric [10-12], it has been shown that the short beam shear strength is a good indication of the interfacial strength and is not significantly affected by the matrix morphology [10]. While fiber/matrix interaction was found to be present in the APC-2 prepreg form, in the NCS-1025 commingled fabric the fiber/matrix interaction has to be created during the molding process. The creation of this interaction was found to be strongly dependent on the molding temperature, the residence time in the melt and the cooling rate [10, 11]. A decrease in the molding temperature resulted in a longer time to reach optimum interfacial strength in the composite. The cooling rate during the processing cycle is also an important parameter which was found to affect the matrix crystallization [11], the matrix morphology and the fiber/matrix adhesion in the composite.

The objective of the present work is to better understand the nature of the fiber/matrix interaction in PEEK/carbon composites made from both prepreg and commingled fabric. The investigation focused on the time-temperature dependence of the short beam shear strength of the composites. Both qualitative and quantitative information on the kinetics of the formation of the fiber/matrix interaction in the PEEK/carbon composite are discussed.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials

The non-woven fabric NCS-1025 consisting of unsized AS4 fibers commingled with (150G) PEEK filaments, was obtained from BASF Structural Materials, Inc. This square-symmetric fabric was specially designed to correspond to two plies of APC-2 prepreg. The conventional APC-2 prepreg tapes consisting of 'VICTREX' PEEK reinforced with unidirectional AS4 graphite fibers were obtained from ICI.

2.2 Processing

To compare the performance of the NCS-1025 fabric with that of the APC-2 composite, square-symmetric cross-ply laminates (containing the same volume fraction of 0° and 90° plies) were compression molded; the stacking sequence of the APC-2 and NCS-1025 cross-ply laminates was [(0/90)_g]_s. Square plaques of 150 mm × 150 mm × 3 mm thick were compression molded in a matched mold using a programmable Wabash press permitting reproducible molding cycles. The plaques were molded between 370°C and 420°C; the temperature of the melt was measured with a thermocouple inserted in the laminates. Heating was done without pressure and when the molding temperature was reached, high pressure was applied. After a given residence time at the molding temperature, the laminates were cooled to room temperature at different rates.

2.3 Mechanical characterization

Short beam shear tests were carried out on samples of 6 mm × 15 mm × 3 mm thick with a ratio of span to specimen thickness of 4. The tests were done on an Instron Machine Model 1025 at 1.3 mm/min following the ASTM-D2344 method.

3. RESULTS

Figure 1 shows the dependence of the performance of the NCS-1025 and APC-2 composites in terms of short beam shear strength upon residence time at a melting temperature of 400°C. The cooling rate was kept constant at 20°C/min. The results show that the performance of APC-2 does not change with the residence time, up to about 120 min. However, the NCS-1025 composite strongly evolves with the residence time. The short beam shear strength in this composite significantly increases with the residence time, attains a maximum value and then decreases. In the APC-2 composite, because good fiber/matrix adhesion already exists in the prepreg form the short beam shear strength is not affected by the residence time until significant degradation of the interphase occurs. In contrast to this, in the commingled system the adhesion has to be created

during molding and the level of fiber/matrix interaction evolves as the residence time at the molding temperature increases. Figure 2 shows the fracture surfaces of the NCS-1025 composite at various residence times at 400°C. At short residence time, no matrix retention is observed on the fiber surface. At very long residence time, corresponding to the drop of the short beam shear strength, the matrix exhibits a brittle fracture pattern with strong fiber matrix interaction, suggesting a degradation of the matrix.

From the above results, it appears that the phenomenon of fiber/matrix interaction in the NCS-1025 PEEK/carbon composite depends on both time and temperature. In their investigation of polycarbonate/carbon fiber composite, Brady and Porter [2] drew the same conclusion and suggested that a physicochemical mechanism like physical adsorption is probably responsible for the creation of fiber/matrix interaction in thermoplastic/carbon fiber composite. As shown in Figure 3, faster rates of increase of the short beam shear strength are observed at higher temperatures. As discussed above, the decrease observed for samples molded at high temperature for long residence times is probably related to the thermal degradation of the matrix.

To explain the creation of the fiber/matrix interaction, it is helpful to imagine a process in which a certain number of adsorption or interaction sites on the carbon fiber surface can be continually filled [2]. In this model, adsorption and desorption occur until an equilibrium is reached, as indicated by the increase in short beam shear strength up to a maximum value (Figure 3). The rate of approach is naturally higher at higher temperature just as in normal chemical kinetics. In the present work, the shape of the curves of Figure 3 allows application of the proposed concept of adsorption. A Langmuir-type equation [13] was thus used to analyze the dependence of short beam shear strength on residence time at each temperature. The kinetic equation can be expressed as:

$$\frac{\Delta S}{\Delta S_{eq}} = \frac{kt}{1+kt} \quad (1)$$

where S is the short beam shear strength measured at the residence time t , $\Delta S = S - S_0$ is the change in short beam shear strength on increasing the residence time, ΔS_{eq} is the equilibrium change in short beam shear strength and k is a kinetic parameter. The value of S_0 which corresponds to the case where there is no fiber/matrix interaction in the composite, is very difficult to evaluate since the total absence of adhesion cannot be absolutely determined. Hence, S_0 was approximated by taking the value of the short beam shear strength measured for the NCS-1025 composite molded at 370°C for a residence time of 1 minute. This composite is characterized by good fiber wetting and by the lower short beam shear strength value of 42 MPa. Rearranging equation (1) to

$$\frac{t}{\Delta S} = \frac{1}{k\Delta S_{eq}} + \frac{t}{\Delta S_{eq}} \quad (2)$$

makes it possible to obtain the kinetic constant and calculate the ΔS_{eq} value. Plotting $t/\Delta S$ versus t gives a linear variation with slope = $1/\Delta S_{eq}$ and intercept = $1/k\Delta S_{eq}$. The calculated parameters obtained for each temperature are presented in Table 1. The calculated curve for S obtained from Equation (1) as a function of residence time at the molding temperature of 380°C is presented in Figure 4. Good accordance between calculated and experimental values indicates that the kinetics of the formation of the fiber/matrix interaction agree with the physicochemical concept of adsorption and can be described by a Langmuir-type expression. According to this model, k (Table 1) is a kinetic parameter and indicates the speed of approaching equilibrium. Its value increases with increasing temperature. This parameter can thus be considered as a measure of a reaction rate. Figure 5 shows that the temperature dependence of this kinetic parameter can be expressed in terms of an Arrhenius equation, $\ln k = Cte - E_a/RT$, which gives to an activation energy, E_a , of 324 kJmol⁻¹ related to the formation of the fiber/matrix interaction in the composite.

Table 1. Calculation of the kinetic constant of the time/temperature dependence of the short beam shear strength performance using a Langmuir-type equation.

Molding temperature °C	ΔS_{eq} MPa	k min ⁻¹	Correlation coefficient
370	62.3	0.052	0.864
380	57.77	0.109	0.988
400	48.74	1.195	0.997
410	39.99	2.468	0.992
420	41.20	3.820	0.999

The cooling rate is another time parameter which can affect the mechanism of the creation of fiber/matrix adhesion in the composite, since a variation of the cooling rate implies a variation of the time spent at high temperature. Moreover, this is also a critical processing parameter which is recognized to affect the thermoplastic matrix morphology in the composite. Figure 6 presents the effect of cooling rate on the short beam shear strength of the APC-2 and the NCS-1025 composites molded at 400°C for a residence time of five minutes. Surprisingly enough, although good fiber/matrix interaction is present in the prepreg system, the short beam shear strength of APC-2 laminate is significantly affected by the cooling rate. While the short beam shear strength decreases only slightly at low cooling rates, a significant drop of about 12% is observed between cooling rates of 20°C/min and 63°C/min. At higher cooling rates, the short beam shear strength reaches a plateau value of about 73 MPa. For the NCS-1025 laminates, a decrease is also observed when the cooling rate is increased. However, in this case above 20°C/min the short beam shear strength decreases continuously with increasing cooling rate.

From microscopic observations and the above mechanical results, a critical cooling rate between 20°C/min and 63°C/min can be associated with a change in the fiber/matrix interaction for the PEEK/carbon composite made from both the commingled and prepreg systems. While microscopic observations of the fracture surfaces show good fiber/matrix interaction for the APC-2 composite whatever the cooling rate, at this critical cooling rate a transition between cohesive and adhesive fracture was observed for the NCS-1025 composite. Moreover, it should be noted that this critical value corresponds closely to that previously observed for the variation of the crystallization temperature as a function of the cooling rate [11], suggesting a strong dependence between strength of the fiber/matrix interaction and crystalline morphology of the PEEK matrix.

However, the interfacial crystallization is not the primary parameter responsible for the creation of fiber/matrix interaction in PEEK/carbon composite. As shown in Table 2, increasing the residence time at the molding temperature of 400°C from 5 min to 60 min produces an NCS-1025 composite which behaves in the same manner as the APC-2 material; an increase of the cooling rate from 20°C/min to 200°C/min produces a reduction of the interfacial strength of about 12%. This difference probably corresponds to the contribution of the interfacial crystallinity to the interfacial strength in the PEEK/carbon composite since, as shown in Table 3, annealing promotes crystallization and results in an increase of the short beam shear strength to about the value for the slowly cooled laminate. From this table, it can be observed that the same annealing experiment performed on the rapidly cooled NCS-1025 laminate leads to equivalent improvement only if the residence time is long enough to permit the creation of strong fiber/matrix interaction. The results clearly demonstrate that a variation of the cooling rate produces a modification of the crystalline morphology of the interphase which consequently affects the interfacial strength of the composite. However, interphase crystallinity is not the sole parameter controlling interfacial strength. Its contribution becomes significant only in the presence of strong physicochemical interaction between the fibers and the matrix. Moreover, this interaction seems to be an irreversible process.

Table 2. Effect of cooling rate on the short beam shear strength of NCS-1025 and APC-2 laminates.

Cooling Rate °C	Residence time (min)		
	NCS-1025		APC-2
20	5	60	5
	79	85	85
200	45	76	74

Table 3. Effect of annealing on the short beam shear strength of rapidly cooled NCS-1025 and APC-2 laminates.

Thermal Treatment	Residence time (min)		
	NCS-1025		APC-2
200°C/min	5	60	5
	45	76	74
Annealing	45	88	87

In fact, if the NCS-1025 composite with strong fiber/matrix interaction (such as obtained with a residence time of 60 min at 400°C) is remelted at 400°C for a very short residence time of 1 min, the fracture surface still shows strong fiber/matrix interaction (Figure 7) with an interfacial strength of 97 MPa. Chemical interaction between the matrix and the highly reactive AS4 carbon fiber could be envisaged since it has been found that thermal modification of the PEEK matrix at its processing temperature is not negligible [14, 15].

5. CONCLUSION

In this work, it has been shown that interfacial crystallinity is essential to insure optimum interfacial strength, but it is not the primary parameter responsible for the creation of the fiber/matrix interaction in PEEK/carbon composite. For the NCS-1025 commingled system the interfacial crystallinity is efficient only if strong fiber/matrix interaction is present in the composite. In terms of processing-property correlation, this interaction is an irreversible process.

The formation of the fiber/matrix interaction in the NCS-1025 PEEK/carbon composite has been found to be time-temperature dependent. The kinetics of the formation of this interaction, as measured by the short beam shear strength in the composite, has been found to agree with the physicochemical concept of adsorption, and can be described by a Langmuir-type expression. The temperature dependence of the formation of the fiber/matrix interaction follows an Arrhenius equation with an activation energy of 324 kJ mol⁻¹. The high value of the activation energy and the irreversibility of the interaction process suggests that chemisorption could be a dominant mechanism since it has been found that in the range of the processing temperature of the PEEK/carbon composite, modification of the matrix (chain scission and crosslinking) as well as thermal degradation leading to reactive species is not negligible.

6. REFERENCES

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Figure 1. Short beam shear strength as a function of residence time at 400°C for the NCS-1025 and APC-2 [(0/90)_g]_s laminates cooled at 20°C/min.

Figure 2. Micrographs of fracture surfaces of the NCS-1025 laminates as a function of residence time at 400°C; (a) 1 min, (b) 5 min and (c) 120 min.

Figure 3. Variation of the short beam shear strength as a function of residence time for the NCS-1025 composites molded at different temperatures.

Figure 4. Predicted and measured short beam shear strength as a function of residence time for the NCS-1025 composite molded at 380°C.

Figure 5. Arrhenius representation of the temperature dependence of the rate parameter k .

Figure 6. Short beam shear strength of the APC-2 and NCS-1025 composites molded at 400°C for a residence time of five minutes and cooled at various rates ranging from $1^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$ to $200^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$.

50 μm

Figure 7. Micrograph of fracture surface of the NCS-1025 laminate molded at 400°C for a residence time of 1 min from a laminate previously molded at 400°C for a residence time of 60 min.